

THE NEED AND PEDAGOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES TO DEVELOP PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE SOCIAL WORKERS

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Abstract: In the article, the new principles of humanization of social structures, the laws of the market economy, ideological and moral principles are changing, unemployment, material shortage, uncontrollable children, separation of families, anti-social phenomena - alcoholism, drug addiction, crime, prostitution, etc. social problems are scientifically analyzed.

Key words: professional competence, social policy, social stability, social protection, communicative skills, reflexive skills

INTRODUCTION

First of all, children, but also adults, need social support and protection. In such conditions, there is a need for a specialist, that is, a future social worker - a social pedagogue, who helps to solve pedagogical issues related to the social problems of a person in the process of socialization of society.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The implementation of socio-pedagogical activities is also explained by the emergence of new democratic values based on ensuring the protection of human rights and rights of citizens. The importance of this issue has been recognized by the management systems of our country since the first days of independence, which can be explained by the following:

1. Declaration of a strong social policy as a priority direction of the republic's development.
2. Adoption of a number of laws and decrees for the protection of low-income sections of the population.
3. Improvement of the material and technical base of former social protection institutions and establishment of new ones.
4. Introduction of the "National Personnel Training Program" as a set of socio-pedagogical measures aimed at forming a well-rounded person.

The issue of ensuring social stability in the lives of the citizens of the new Uzbekistan occupies an important place in the works and speeches of President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev. They emphasize that humanity and kindness are an integral feature of the Uzbek people, and many problems of a social nature: health care, improving the material and technical base of schools and hospitals, building sports complexes, helping large families, and others. a number of issues are being discussed[1].

Who is a social worker and what are his duties? A social worker is a person who organizes the provision of social services or directly provides social services with the necessary professional qualifications[2].

The following are defined as the main tasks and areas of activity of social workers in "Inson" social service centers:

providing professional social services based on a complex approach directly at the neighborhood level to individuals and families who are in a serious situation and are at high risk of falling into a serious situation;

developing plans to provide individual social services and assistance to the population in need of social protection by assessing their needs and available opportunities;

organizing the provision of social services and assistance in accordance with the plan of individual social services, as well as making relevant amendments to the plan of individual social services in necessary cases;

attracting internal resources, including social support volunteers (relatives, neighbors, volunteers) to provide social services and assistance, and coordinating their activities in this field;

social services guaranteed by the state to the population

and providing an explanation about assistance, as well as the rights of the population to receive these services. In this case, the heads of state bodies and organizations are personally responsible and accountable for providing all-round assistance to social workers in the provision of social services and assistance[3].

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

So, a social worker provides work and services aimed at overcoming social problems of individuals and families in difficult social situations and creating conditions for them to enjoy equal opportunities with other individuals in society.

Active participation of all employees is required in the process of providing high-quality social services that meet modern requirements. All aspects of activation of social services should be reflected in the decisions made by the team members.

In general, the communication skills of a social worker consist of the following specific features:

1. Social-psychological forecasting of the basis of the communicative situation in which communication can be carried out.

2. Social-psychological programming of the communication process, self, in which special attention is paid to the uniqueness of the communicative situation.
3. Implementation of communication processes in a communicative situation with features of socio-psychological management[4].

Communicative ability "is not an innate ability, it is an ability that is formed by a person in the process of acquiring social-communicative experience. Communicative-social experience, first of all, includes the mechanism of changing relations and is manifested in the use of speech in stylistically different options. The basis of such a change is the change of role communication between the participants of the dialogue" [5].

A careful study of the nature and structure of the teacher's communicative abilities allowed us to distinguish two, interrelated and interconnected levels: the first level, directly, the manifestation of communicative competence in communication itself determines, that is, in the communicative behavior of a person; the second one should introduce pedagogical and communicative values through the specific characteristics and orientation of the teacher's professional motivation, his special need for communication.

When all the considered components are combined, the essence of communicative ability is clearly shown and forms the most complex qualities of the human personality that are interdependent and mutually demanding. As a result, communicative ability appears as one of the important professionally oriented characteristics of the pedagogue's skill, and the development of this ability is the first task in higher professional education. Modern stages of the development of society, new paradigms in education - all this fills the problem of communication skills development with new content.

Here are the following:

- a teacher engaged in pedagogical activity develops personal characteristics related to each other such as ability, communicative ability, pedagogical ability through constant work on himself, which serves as a basis for him to become a skilled professional;
- the specific pedagogical conditions of communicative ability, pedagogical reflection, directions, skill criteria are an important factor in demonstrating his professional competence and sharpening his personal ability;
- technological design, algorithmization of the educational process, pre-diagnosis of the result and its innovative management are of great importance in demonstrating the communicative ability of people and improving their skills;

- communicative abilities are interpreted as a set of integrated competencies combined with empathic and reflexive abilities. It can be developed with the help of special training sessions[6].

Perceptive ability: perception, perception of the external world and environment, i.e. observation plays an important role. Perceptive-pedagogical skills (lat. "perceptio" - mastery) - the ability to enter the inner world of a person, psychological observation, the ability to understand subtle aspects of the student's mental state [7].

According to N.V. Kuzmina, the "content of reflection is the subjective re-creation of the partner's inner world on the basis of mutual cooperation, when individuals reflect each other as in a mirror, a unique duality process of mutual reflection, moreover, this in the inner world, in turn, the inner world of the first researcher is reflected." He studies reflection from the point of view of pedagogical abilities, and for the first time distinguishes the reflexive-perceptive abilities of a person as a separate component. N.V. Kuzmina emphasizes that the formation of pedagogical intuition depends on the level of formation of reflexive pedagogical skills. "Good intuition is manifested when the teacher extrapolates information about the most noble, positive qualities of the student, which can be relied on to achieve the desired results (applying the conclusions based on the observation of one phenomenon to other situations)" [8].

Perceptive ability is the first basic structure of the perception process, which consists in learning the objects of perception and comparing it with memory images. Observability, which is the most important element of a person's perceptive characteristics, develops and improves both in the process of creating a person's social experience and as a result of his special efforts [9].

It develops and improves as a result of the enthusiasm of the social worker. A social worker perceives the psychology and mental state of a citizen, makes a fair assessment of the state of the community.

Empathic ability: the feeling that comes from love for people, feeling their psychological state from the heart, understanding, perceiving, feeling pity for them.

It can be said that an empath is a telepath who can read minds with restraint, but can understand the emotional state of another person directly from the first person. Therefore, in people with a strong level of empathy in this regard, if, due to this phenomenon, they stop distinguishing and recognizing their feelings, as a rule, from the feelings of relatives and people close to them, various psychological disorders develop.[10].

The term "empathy" was introduced into psychology to indicate an inner dynamism, the result of which is an unconscious understanding of another person's situation. Modern formulations of empathy may include:

- knowing and understanding the inner state of another person's thoughts and feelings;
- "emotion" in emotional states, which is the second;
- The activity of reconstructing another person's feelings with the help of imagination;
- Thinking about how a person can behave in another person's place;
- Grief in response to another person's suffering;
- emotional feedback directed at the other person, consistent with the person's understanding of the other's happiness, etc.

In other words, true empathy involves not only a high level of emotional acceptance, but also a high level of awareness. On the basis of the first two components, an incentive to help another appears, which motivates the child to specific actions. As a result, we can conclude that an increase in the level of empathy consists of:

- Cognitive component, which includes understanding the feelings of another person in a particular situation.
- The emotional component is empathy.
- A behavioral component that may include actions that positively affect the feelings and state of another person. It should be noted that there are no universal signs for defining the concept of empathy. You can identify some cumulative qualities that reveal the essence of empathy. True empathy involves not only a high emotional sensitivity to others, but also a high value of understanding other people. Based on sympathy and empathy, there is an impulse to contribute, an impulse that motivates various actions[11].

In the course of the research, theoretical information was gathered that reveals the nature of the following important ex-extensional components necessary for the formation of the personality in the mutaxacic quality: pedagogical competence, duty, conscience, freedom, responsibility. The pedagogical competence of the person was analyzed above. We concluded that it is appropriate to analyze the sources that highlight the unique aspects of the problem of the formation of pedagogical knowledge, skills and qualifications of future social workers. Proper use of such pedagogical skills in educating future social workers with high professional culture and important professional and personal qualities is one of the important tasks for the current period.

Pedagogical activity, in a word, is a necessary activity, the purpose of which is to introduce the young generation to the culture and values of Christianity and prepare them for life. In the process of education and training, the future social worker's possession of various qualities guarantees a comprehensive result. The positive qualities are:

- competence with social and personal human qualities;
- solving society's problems;
- honoring students;
- faith in the future;
- justice;
- high demands on oneself and the students;
- critically evaluate one's own work;
- initiative;
- willingness;
- liability insurance;
- creativity;
- intelligence and others[12].

The professional qualities and pedagogical competence are one of the most important qualities that should be present in the work of a pedagogue. Such a positive quality does not appear by itself. It is formed and developed as a result of systematic exposure to students over the years.

In general, the issue of professional competence can be approached from the point of view of different disciplines. Its structure reflects sociological, psychological, culturological, religious, and personal content, and it is distinguished by its complexity during scientific study. If competence is a psychological and professional requirement for a person to work successfully during his professional activity, a prerequisite for acquiring a professional skill, specialty, i.e., the requirements imposed by the profession on the holder of the profession, if we define it in the form of personal qualities that should be formed in a specialist during the acquisition of a specialty, then it is appropriate to study it in a systematic way.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, professional competence means a person's professionalism in a general sense, that is, the combination of his theoretical and practical experiences in one or another field. At the same time, competence means the presence of a person's abilities to perform this or that activity and the level of development of these abilities. Today, the development of professional

competence of future specialists in higher education institutions is one of the main issues. In this regard, we believe that it is appropriate to carry out systematic work in the following directions:

Firstly, on the basis of the reforms in the educational system implemented today, in order to expand the worldview of specialists and increase their initiative based on creativity, it is necessary to organize the training process in such a way that the cadets consciously and actively acquire professional knowledge and methods of their practical application. to focus on ensuring that it serves the development of independence, creativity, thinking, speech technique in creative initiative and educational activities.

Secondly, in the era of digital economy, implementation of ways to form and develop the professional competence of specialists based on the requirements of the time.

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